

PSYCHOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CHARACTER OF A "PARANORMAL" HUMAN CHARACTER IN "THE STRANGER"

Ghiyasov Mirali

Uzbekistan state world languages university teacher

Petra Runge

University of Kempten , Germany teacher

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Annotation

Human body and soul from unity organize found Both to themselves regularly requires food . The body material blessings feeds our soul while spiritual food I need it . Of them where one lacks " eat " . since , one unstoppable one day he to destruction face holds.

Key words: "The Stranger", modernism, postmodernism, absurd philosophy, literary critic;
Past in the century humanity of development high peaks conquest did Unprecedented level inventions human , humanity progress with together service to decline did In particular, the atomic bomb invention to be done humanity of destruction foundation it has been. Spiritual feed lack of power has been love is love priest world-heart destruction to the edge take come put Second the world war humanity not only physically death did, maybe spirit. It's also important. This condition especially literature and art people representatives to his creativity significant level effect spent This depression as a result this the world events with fix it considering that it will not be the main thing attention to the boot focused started " Man in real life not but only in his mind happy be he said to look of modernism appear to be and strong impetus to development it has been .

With that together, completely to despair fall started in society existentialism direction to the composition entered absurdism ideas are also earlier push started This is it period in art this views reflection and the literature is also new one in the image manifestation it has been. In fact , the world of wars himself illogical effort actions was Suffering and horrible war the writer and poets in his thinking not only from the battle , that's it with together , the meaning of life to find they don't get it with manifestation it has been. So by doing their some of them of humanity life the meaning search on the way actions consider it unreasonable they started

Absurdism ideas influenced , in particular , by A. Camus , F. Dostoevsky , F. Nietzsche, A. France like writers creativity sprout came out Many researchers our analysis in the object "The Stranger " by Albert Camus absurdism ideas before drove work as evaluated . But a literary critic Uzok Dzhorakulov his own " Without territory " jilva " is scientific in his work story about the following thoughts said pass work and his to the hero new look with to look at encourages :

" Murso fate solution did things are actually real is logic . Why , him inevitable death contemporaries who " rewarded " with Real life, which Meursault considered absurd image that it is denial reached it won't be . That's exactly it In a sense, I consider the story "The Stranger" to be an absurd work not absurd philosophy inevitable destruction expression reached literature example to say tend to "

Meursault about sure one to stop to arrive and conclusion to do in the beginning above telling as we passed , Mersoni to the world brought time , era thinking about to do need Simple one life style forgiving a person such in the situation only fear and hope , perhaps , despair with life sorry , but high and thin heart owners has been art and literature people such to the situation just look throw away ca n't Especially like Camus deep philosophical thinking the owners heavy depression and experiences from the beginning sorry no doubt Meursault is the same that's it experiences , thinking lines , world and humanity about conclusions product He just is tissue as " born " in literature no his to the world arrival in the 20th century passing literary process and spiritual to experiences depend

Above Meursault image formation etymology little about thought we walked And now the main character character look if we throw

A lot of people work just beginning start to surprise . Hero of his mother his death carelessly own from the language statement does Neighbor yes something a stranger death about that's it way thought notice is probably normative is the case , but own mother about coolly thought conduct of humanity something to the criterion right does not come and work from the beginning apparently as the novel has paranormal properties have person his life story does " Today my mother died , yes last night I don't know " Mother from message didn't get and this important not dated (this because of to him earlier message did not give !) hero this is the speech . He is " mother died , " he says , " from my mother I lost " not " . Of that sentence himself inhuman , exceptional image that it is showing

" Your mother death did Burial tomorrow Deep sympathy let us know " said telegram received a child what is for only of the message Incomprehensibility , which mother is actually day death did the fact that about just thinks . " You don't understand . Maybe yesterday must have died " At first in the paragraph only sentences whole head work the pathos managed stands Mersoni is not a "paranormal character " , but a "paranormal character". have It is not for nothing that we describe it as " a person " . it's not . Actually , Merson's character usual male character as embodied . Of course , his to his mother has been relationship humanity for very painful condition But the mentality and faith to the issue if we evaluate according to his parents the elderly home submit normative condition Of course , long term interruption and from separation after Meursault is the same to the situation gets used to it and relationship is also somewhat cools down . Surface than Meursault very cold hearted human But this from showing of the writer purpose what Merson condemn ?

Psychologist and creator John Gray in his " From Heaven fell children " in the work " West free life education to the tension take is coming " said thoughts said passes . Moreover , the psychologist stated , " Children problems at home begins and that's it on the ground solution to be done can ." Merson's his parents with relationship from that too come out unbiased conclusion to do it is necessary

Meursault in childhood how that it was about in the work , including the hero in his memories , almost , he did not stop. In this place only two information to bring possible : Meursault his father does not know about him only from his mother heard , of his mother personal qualities about and " mother " let's if not but in his lifetime also interested in religion did not see was " , saying remembers This condition while Meursault character formation effect did not to be possible it's not . Apparently Meursault since childhood physically loneliness from the beginning sorry lived Fatherless , alone mother with . Later on and his mother with also to separation encountered Meursault to loneliness the whole adapting was That's it from the

diagnosis come out of his mother death in time himself catch the situation we Meursault for natural I consider it a condition we can. That's it childhood formed environment, living style Merson's people with communication limiting put his for that's it loneliness, small in his room single, milky coffee drinking newspaper study interesting condition That's it from people interrupt, empty left until he said own to the shell wrap around get as a result of that society with how communication to do he doesn't even know the way.

With that together , child's to mother has been relationship your father to mother has been relationship with , of the child morality while your father ethics model based on is formed . In our hero and such condition no.

Meursault own his mother the elderly at home left He is very cold hearted and unfeeling , unloving . In this place one question born : old people at home only Merson's mother residence does it only Meursault numb and are you cold ? The rest own his parents in the orphanage those who left affectionate , cold isn't it ? of the West degenerative , painful point too the same then The thing is , only Mersogina heart openly show takes , own personality unmasked manifestation do it takes The same that's it character from the feature come out we Mersoni is a paranormal person that say we can

Meursault long term from interruption after of his mother how many age too does n't know That's right , he's with Marie entertainment will do to him that he doesn't love says because him really too does not love To the cinema go , sleep releases One it looks very cold- blooded But , in fact , it is different of men too mind under hidden desire and desires , simply , openly done increases , the words with represents Attention we give , " men's " above mind under " the sentence we used Male and a woman psychology from each other fundamentally difference does That's why for also means " humans " . summarizing to apply must we didn't find it . Our opinion proof as of psychologist John Gray this to the topic dedicated to " Men - Mars, women and from the planet Venus in the book to the facts our attention if we look at : " The Martians interests , people and to the senses not to " subject " , " thing " . directed ."

" Usually , men themselves warmth and from delicacy how many speed and cruelty with numb and alienation apparently to come account they don't get He is his in the cave the problem of sitting solution while doing , to others how much damage is bringing even doesn't even think ."

This is it psychological from the data come out , in Merso this circumstances consider it natural we can However , in the work the most attention attraction who does one sentence he is the main character from the language work from the introduction until the end very a lot applied . He is " essentially never thing that has changed no " , is the sentence . Yes, it's his mother's funeral in the ceremony cigarette smoked , coffee drank - own needs satisfied - natural desire He is this things unmasked done only increased . He himself forced cry He just didn't get it mask did not wear , role did not play The child is from the mother give up late day his mother is for him dying has been was

But, Meursault how many honest , sincere don't be his this qualities no issuer one vice there is was in character . It's his indifference " I'm done came First coffin next to how I hesitated . Then what the difference there is I said . 9

Merson's from society different to them you don't understand or their hatred instigator being visible actions at the core the same what is this the difference is there ?" said reasoning there is . This is the end from informality expanded to crime take went It is the first time to Arab

bullet extending and after repeatedly bullet stretch exactly that's it in view was :
"What's the difference is there ?" Joiner to him friendship offer even if he does loved a woman marriage to build wanting , not wanting even if he asks the answer the same that's it . Camus to the work crime with depends Khodiasni by entering this way look how consequences take to come showing gives

Well , to Meursault " what the difference is there ?" said look root where ? He is life only that's it from the world knows that it consists , man and everyone thing one day finish it is never what important owner thought not or life essence you understand I don't know was

Raymond Arabic to kill about from the mind first back , that's it to work " this after all the pig after evaluating his work and " shot even if he throws , on the contrary , even if he does n't , what the difference to think that there is in it little first Raymond from murder back showed conscientiousness no releases In prison late days during Merson's a lot there is about Marie memories remember from taking book reader initially him to a woman he thinks he 's in love . However , his "I never when Marie's himself what i thought no Just that one woman , in general women , what I saw all about and which one with when , where that I joined I think that 's it until a lot than i thought detention center their to their faces full go to my wishes narrowness by doing remains " sentences hero about thoughts the whole by changing sends Mother with depends memories Remember Meursault mother with lived at the time house saranjom only that it was confession is enough Hero's this character feature about academic U.Jorakulov the following thoughts means :

"Neither to the society , nor to his mother , no to the mistress , no to a friend from the relationship meaning to find received Meursault , for what reason horrible crime - murder more than he did meaning to find can't ."

Merson's pay attention to speech giving if we are , he is to death judgment to be done not even until he doesn't feel anything . Speech is also only and only objects , material things about thought conducted by : Marie's a lawyer 's hat necklace , Salamano of the old man face , hair , purple ink is filled square inkwell and lime

Meursault even in prison too situation indifferently expresses : "Very good that's all little by little of justice himself care I thought he would ." These are the sentences of the hero even his own in detention in prison that that he doesn't even feel pity means Writer Meursault from the language very deep considerations cause passes . To them stops in the library a person each how to adapt to the conditions , every how in the case itself there is of blessings pleasure find the comforts to find necessity about passion should do views wakes up . But in Meursault this condition his piety , willful that , from patience , to life has been from love proof does not give It's his decline set giver the most bottom aspect to be from indifference is evidence . On the street , at home , in prison , in freedom , to him the difference no , - just his physical needs if satisfied it has been . Even in prison he is alone about these (women , cigarettes). thinks None how emotional experience one to him Meursault though from the heart place ca n't Because himself as noted , " what the difference is there ?".

Meursault character truthfulness , sincerity , simplicity , self in disguise show not to get , to the situation flexibility around of people (Marie, Raymon, Salamano , Celeste) . some of them to him towards aspiration reason will be , however in the hero indifference , loneliness aspiration him to people spirit approach road does not give One word with in other words , to society a stranger by doing puts That's it indifference vice about german writer Georg Lichtenberg " Where indifference is there error where coolness is there crime definition gives

Indeed, Meursault character this aspects the writer above telling as passed the hero encourages mistakes and crimes. Indifferent people about also the first our president Islam Karimov also announced his "Yuksak spirituality is invincible power" this thoughts said passes: "From enemies don't be afraid - go ahead if it goes they are you to kill can From friends don't be afraid - go ahead if it goes they are to you betrayal to do can Indifferent from people fear them you neither kill nor sell, only their quiet and careless looking standing because of land on the face betrayal and murders appear will be."

Society this such as people the same that's it to the situation cause to put realized without Camus also called Mersoni "to death." judgment will do." Why Arab? from before him to kill intended by Raymon not exactly Meursault by killed? After all, Raymon is also different shame at work enthusiasm showed was it? Raymon the Arab to kill wanted, why, then to those around relatively good and bad there is a relationship. However, in Meursault this indifference society Raymond's from the shortcomings according to more to decline face it catches In particular, the doorman is the "separation" of loneliness, itself from others excess which he considers to be superior image as described But he is also from "stranger". safer.

Meursault own to his life the meaning all material of things looking for sees (women, various food, drink release). That's exactly why for he himself lived from life never one meaning to find can't. Because he is human to his life content material, formal it's not spiritual of the universe increase, saturation through come in goes Spiritual universe and religion is to God has been love and hope in the family high moral education in society mutually affection for love kneaded relationships as a result full goes Mercado while this such as of possibilities there is none. of society his own mask open if you look at it millions of Mersos meeting can to Meursault high moral education to give possible has been mother while of spirituality the most the first basically has been religious - moral from the rules unaware one woman In general when, a person character formation very a lot of a person to himself depends was not, but himself with depends factors cause will be

To the heart mask catch received "in fact It is full of Mersos in society Prosecutor such as only and only own interest (in court win output) for Merson's true to speak, even later regret to be, vindicator of the parties to his thoughts for him regardless death punishment who asks people actually identity to hide tried indifferent, good actors

Summary by doing in the words of Albert Camus this image in character cool, own in his life the meaning lost, truthful, sincere, but to everyone relatively indifferent person image embodied and this image through whole one the true image of society showing to give goal did

References:

- 1.Ulugbek Hamdamov. WORLD LITERATURE: MODERNISM AND POSTMODERNISM (study manual). Tashkent, "Akademnashr" - 2020
- 2.The best works of John Gray. Men are Mars, women and from the planet Venus. "BOOK MEDIA PUBLICATION". TASHKENT - 2020.
- 3.Albert Camus. "Stranger". "New century generation". Tashkent - 2014.
- 4.Uzok Dzhorakulov. Without territory jilva - Tashkent: Science, 2006.